

Figure Z3

Figure Z3: Different representations of single-cell maps for each tissue. a-c, Single-cell maps of scWAT (**A**), vWAT (**B**) and SkM (**C**) across four intervention groups. The tSNE and UMAP plots in each panel are coloured by tissue type, intervention group, *Ptpcr* expression, sample, and cell type. A list of abbreviations used in this figure appear in the Methods.